

DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE LEARNING MODULES IN AUTOMOTIVE TECHNOLOGY: A VALIDATION STUDY

Rogelio N. Tandayu, LPT, MAIE

Isabela State University-City of Ilagan Campus, Isabela, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14202048>

ABSTRACT

The growing demand for skilled automotive technicians and educators highlights the critical need for effective instructional materials in technical education. However, there is a lack of well-designed and validated learning modules specifically made to address key competencies in automotive technology. This study aimed to develop and validate learning modules in automotive technology to support effective skill acquisition among students. Using the Isman Instructional Model, the research followed a systematic process involving needs assessment, module design, expert evaluation, and iterative revisions based on peer feedback. The modules, which focused on the topics of servicing engine mechanical systems, included structured elements such as objectives, practice tasks, and feedback sections. To test their effectiveness, a pre-test/post-test experimental design was employed with two groups: an experimental group using the modules and a control group receiving traditional lectures. Statistical analyses revealed significantly higher post-test scores for the experimental group, confirming the modules' effectiveness in enhancing student learning and retention. The findings suggest that these validated learning modules are valuable instructional tools in automotive technology education, with potential applications across technical and vocational training contexts to promote interactive, learner-centered education.

Keywords: *Learning Modules, Automotive Technology, Isman Instructional Model, Pre-test/Post-test Experimental Design, Skill Acquisition*

INTRODUCTION

Education is the most effective agent for social change and national development. It is through education that a country is provided with productive manpower that carries out societal transformation and progress. Schools at all curriculum levels are tasked to provide learners with the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitudes that will prepare them as active contributors to national growth and development (Victory, 2011; Jahantab, 2021; Adu, 2021)

A major sub-system of education dealing with the technological aspects of the environment is technology education. It deals with the development of technical knowledge, skills, and attitudes needed to enter into and/or progress in the world of work or prepare people for productive and meaningful citizenship. The goals and objectives of technology education focus on improving the quality of technical education with the view of producing skilled and middle-level technical workforce for the manpower needs of the industrial sector; promoting industry-based training education in technical skills; establishing stronger and functional linkages with the business and industry sectors; developing entrepreneurial competencies of future industrialists/students that will lead and motivate them for self-employment; inculcating work values and right attitudes for effectiveness and efficiency in the job; and promoting and strengthening the quality of technical education and skills development programs of the university to attain regional, national, and international competitiveness (Odo, et. al 2017; Mangundayao, et. al, 2011; Ghani & Abdullah, 2002).

The College of Industrial Technology and Education, one of the colleges of the Isabela State University, City of Ilagan Campus, offers a Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education major in Automotive Technology. Its curriculum is ladderized, meaning that after completing the first two years of the curriculum, enrolled students undergo a screening process to continue the four-year degree program. It has been observed that few graduates of the BTTE ladderized program qualify for the screening process. This presents challenges for the researcher, who aims to encourage students in the program to increase their efforts to improve their academic performance. These challenges led to the development and validation of learning modules, which are deemed crucial to supplement and address the students' needs.

In view of the above-cited objectives and in consideration of the present educational system as well as the need for our country to become globally competitive, students are being trained to the utmost of their capabilities through the use of modern instructional materials and modules, which play a vital role in the attainment of the goals and objectives of technology education (Chuks, & Nebechi, 2016; Manabat, 2021; Maiwada, 2022). The act of teaching is so complex that it cannot be said that a specific way of teaching is superior to other ways for all purposes, with all teachers, with all students, for all times and circumstances. Certain procedures, teaching styles, and techniques that are generally not recommended seem to work well for a specific teacher. There is no fast rule in the choice of the best strategy to be used in teaching. The teacher

should adapt different strategies of teaching to suit the needs of the students (Parsons, & Vaughn, 2014; Ramos, 2015).

The skill of selecting the right strategies in the context of a particular lesson is critical (Miller, & Veatch, 2010; Kistner, 2015). The teacher should be knowledgeable and observant enough on how the students learn to be able to apply the appropriate teaching techniques and strategies.

Apostol, et. al (2016) claimed that successful classroom instruction depends upon the technique of teaching; through it, the learning activity of the learners is guided. Without the organization of effort and material to achieve a definite goal, time and effort would be wasted, and satisfactory results in content learned or study habits would not be achieved. It is the teaching technique that provides this guidance for the learners.

For more than three years that the researcher has been teaching this trade area, he observed that with technology revolutionizing education, teachers at all levels need to assess their classroom practices since technology implies that learning activities are based on applied knowledge in most of the content of the subjects.

Based on the CMO No. 56, series of 2007, the success of instruction in the teaching-learning process is not only reliant on traditional methods, but the use of instructional materials like learning modules can also enhance instruction. A learning module is presented to the learners for activities inside the classroom, where the desired knowledge and skills of the learners are developed. The need for developing and validating learning modules greatly uplifts the interest of learners. As such, classroom activities are given priority attention because it is the classroom where the action is, where all learners are involved in learning interaction (Chen & Wang, 2014).

Therefore, it is in the classroom where the lessons are taught, instructional materials and methods are introduced by teachers, and learners acquire learning tasks and skills. The learners are evaluated through performance. Moreover, classrooms can be organized for a better environment so that the learners can experience and achieve better performance in the teaching-learning process. To make teaching effective, the researcher ardently wanted to develop and validate the learning modules in automotive technology, particularly in servicing engine mechanical systems.

The purposes of a Learning Module are: first, to individualize (or to permit the use of teams of learners in) instruction; second, to provide a conceptual model for learning that minimizes the need for conventional, verbalized, instructional techniques; third, to enable (or require) teachers to analyze the learning process; fourth, to improve instruction through better evaluation resulting from the formulation and measurement of learning outcomes expressed in measurable terms; fifth, to maximize the effective use of instructional media and group exercises; and last, to permit learning to occur outside the presence of the teacher (Ricard, 1990).

The researcher is currently teaching subjects in Automotive Technology, which include lessons on servicing engine mechanical systems. For the three years of teaching this course, he has encountered challenges in teaching the skills using the high-technology facilities found in the automotive laboratory, such as the different engines with remote control and color-coded devices. Furthermore, one of the reasons for developing learning modules is that the researcher is also engaged in the Extension and Training Services Program, in which the provision of training related to automotive technology is also conducted for different extension program beneficiaries.

It is for these reasons that the researcher developed and validated instructional modules that can be complementary to the facilities available and may encourage the students to understand the concepts and develop their technical skills using these learning modules. The modules may be used as an alternative delivery mode in teaching lessons. These modules in automotive technology include lessons on servicing the cooling system, lubricating system, and fuel system of an automobile. Automobile servicing will allow the learners to learn the basic knowledge and skills in automotive servicing. The unit on servicing engine mechanical systems covers the knowledge, skills, and attitudes required for an automotive servicing course. The learning modules are envisioned to be user-friendly, suited to the level of the students, and responsive to the current demands of the shop and the industrial sector.

Research Questions

This research study aimed to develop and validate learning modules in servicing mechanical systems. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. How do automotive technology experts evaluate the module based on the following quality elements?
 - a. suitability of learning objectives
 - b. clarity of Instruction and test items
 - c. modules suitability and content
 - d. modules sequence and layout
 - e. modules timing and phasing
 - f. modules suitability of approach
2. What is the pre-test score for both the control and experimental groups?
3. What is the post-test score for both the control and experimental groups?
4. Is there any significant difference in the pre-test scores of the students exposed to the traditional and modular teaching approaches?
5. Is there any significant difference in the post-test scores between the control and experimental groups?
6. What is the average normalized gain score of the students in the control and experimental group?
7. Is there a significant difference in the normalized gain score of the students in the control and experimental group?

METHODOLOGY

The research methodology of this study is divided into two phases: Phase 1 is the development of learning modules and Phase 2 is the validation of the learning modules.

Phase 1. Development of the Module

This study made use of the Isman Instructional Model (2011) in the Development of the Learning Module (Figure 1). This model involves five steps: Input, Process, Output, Feedback, and Learning. Employing this model, activities were documented in the work log in Table 1.

Table 1. Isman Instructional Model (2011) for the design and development of Learning Modules in Automotive Technology (Servicing Engine Mechanical Systems)

Steps	Work Log	Description
Step 1 – Input	Identify the needs Identify the contents Identify goals-objectives Identify teaching methods Identify Evaluation Materials Identify Instructional Media	Assessed/evaluated students' knowledge of technical skills. Identified the contents based on the syllabus in Servicing Engine Mechanical System. Designed the learning modules in Servicing Engine Mechanical Systems. Set the goals and objectives of the learning modules Designed the evaluation techniques based on the objectives of the learning modules

Step 2- Process	Testing prototypes Redesigning instruction Teaching Activities	The learning modules evaluated by a group of experts The learning modules were redesigned based on the suggestions of the experts. The learning modules were used for small group of students for initial perception. Learning modules were modified to small group of students for initial perception The learning modules were modified to suit students' preferences
Step 3 – Output	Assess and Revise Instrument	The learning modules were used for instruction.
Step 4 – Feedback	Revise Instruction	Revised the learning modules based on the comments given by students and teachers
Step 5 – Learning	Learning	Pre-test / Post-test were conducted to test the effectiveness of the module.

The first step in the work log is the input. The researcher justified the observations in developing the technical skills of the students. A needs assessment analysis was conducted. There was a set of activities given to the Bachelor of Teacher Technical Education students to test their knowledge and technical skills in Servicing Engine Mechanical Systems.

Learning objectives were formulated and enhanced. Moreover, learning elements were also planned based on each of the set of objectives which includes the presentation of concepts, sample exercises, and practice tasks. Compiling all of these, yielded to compose self-paced instructional material called learning modules.

The learning modules in Servicing Engine Mechanical Systems consist of the following parts:

1. Title Page

This part includes the module title and the name of the author.

2. Introductory Statement

This part is a motivating statement for the learning module per se. It gives inspiration to the

learners to go through and complete the learning modules.

3. Instruction on how to use the learning modules

This part gave a general instruction on how to use the learning modules for greater effectiveness.

4. Learning Objectives

A general objective for the learning modules is stated. Each learning element has specific learning objectives. Students should be able to attune to these objectives to be prepared for the succeeding activities.

5. Learning Elements

a. Input – It is the main learning activity of the learning modules. It is where terms, topics, and principles are discussed and illustrated along with examples to provide the learner the opportunity to attain the set objectives.

b. Practice Tasks – These are varied ways to assess the learning on the topic presented. It is in the form of an activity that will assess the attainability of the objectives of the learning modules and enhance the acquired learning.

c. Feedback – It is the key to corrections on the Practice Tasks. Students are given a chance to assess their output in the learning modules by simply evaluating their good and weak points and be able to go back to the part of the learning activity wherein it needs some reinforcement.

The next step in the learning modules is the process. The learning modules were subjected to peer review. These modules were given to automotive technology teachers for constructive feedback, recommendations, and evaluation. A checklist was provided for the face evaluation and established criteria about the learning objectives, directions, materials, and learning activities. Additional comments were written on the draft to further improve the learning modules. In addition, an English critic has evaluated the learning modules as per the correctness of grammar and spelling.

Suggestions were incorporated into the learning modules and subjected to evaluation.

The third step is the output which highlights the testing and analyzing results. In this research, the learning modules were used for instruction in class.

The fourth step is the feedback. In the implementation of the learning modules, corrections were expected.

The last step is the Learning. In the implementation of the learning modules, a pretest and posttest were conducted to test their effectiveness.

Phase II. Validation of the Learning Modules

Research Design

This research study made use of the pre-test/post-test experimental design to determine the effect of the learning modules on the student's achievement. The design that was used is shown in the figure below, where E_1 is the pre-test, E_2 is the post-test of the experimental group and X_1 is the treatment (learning modules). C_1 is the pre-test, and C_2 is the post-test of the control group who was exposed to the traditional lecture method X_2 . This research study involved two groups of respondents which were referred to as the experimental group and control group. Their performance was compared before and after the treatment (learning modules). The same set of questionnaires were used in the pre-test and post-test. Hence, an increase in scores in the post-test signified the effectiveness of the treatment (learning modules). Finally, the method used by the researcher in selecting the group of respondents was systematic sampling.

Pre-Test	Methods	Post-Test
E_1	X_1	E_2
C_1	X_2	C_2

Figure 1. The Pre-Test/ Post-Test experimental design

Respondents and Sampling Procedure

Phase I- Development and Evaluation of Module

There is only one group of respondents in this phase, the automotive technology instructors in the campuses of Isabela State University offering automotive technology which includes two (2) from ISU- City of Ilagan Campus, two (2) from ISU-Angadanan Campus and two (2) from ISU-City of Cauayan Campus. A total of six (6) evaluators were involved in the evaluation of the module.

Phase II – Validation of Module

In the validation of the modules, the study involved the students in the College of Industrial Technology and Education particularly the second-year BTTE students, majoring in automotive technology during the second semester, SY. 2016-2017. The twenty (20) students were chosen through paired observations and they were subjected to pre-test and post-test in which the same set of test items was administered and results were tabulated.

Instruments

The primary instruments in this study were the learning modules: Service Cooling System, Service Lubricating System, and Service Fuel System. The experimental group

used the learning modules while the control group was exposed to the traditional lecture method.

This research study adopted the Criteria for Face Validation of Modules which was used by Ricardo (2016) in her study entitled “Development and Validation of Learning Modules in Physics”.

Data Gathering Procedure

A request letter to conduct the research study addressed to the College Dean was prepared and submitted for approval. Upon approval, a pre-test was administered to the Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education second-year students. Pre-test scores were tabulated and respondents were selected through paired observations. Twenty (20) students from Bachelor of Technical Teacher Education were selected as respondents of the study. The first ten (10) were considered the control group and the other ten (10) were the experimental group.

After the feedback, students were given the second set of learning modules. Post-test was administered after completing it.

On the other hand, the control group was given a lecture regarding the topics in the learning modules. After completing all the topics in the learning modules, a post-test was administered. Test papers were checked and post-test scores were presented and analyzed in the class to note their strengths and weaknesses, then the topics of the second set of learning modules were given to them. After completing the lecture, the second set of post-tests was administered. Test papers were checked and discussed with them and their scores were recorded.

Test papers of the respondents of the study (for the post-test) were separated from the file of corrected test papers. Scores were tabulated and interpreted based from the research questions.

Statistical Treatment

This research study made use of the following statistical tools:

Phase I- Development and Evaluation of Learning Modules

The evaluation of the group of experts (Automotive Technology Teachers) was tabulated. Mean scores were computed per criteria and group of criteria to determine which part of the learning modules the group of experts agreed with.

The weighted mean was interpreted using a five-point Likert scale as follows:

Scale	Range	Descriptive title
5	4.20- 5.00	Strongly agree
4	3.4 – 4.19	Agree
3	2.6 – 3.39	Neither agree nor disagree
2	1.80 – 2.59	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree

Mean and Standard Deviation were used to compare the responses across item criteria.

Phase II – Validation of Learning Modules

The pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents were tabulated. To test the effectiveness of the learning modules, the scores of the experimental group and the control group were compared.

Mean scores were computed. To test if there is a significant difference between the experimental and control groups, two samples paired t-test for means were used for both pre-test and post-test scores.

Learning Gain (Hoke Gain) was obtained individually for each respondent. The group learning gain was also computed. The purpose of identifying the learning gain was to establish the amount learned by the respondents using the two modes of teaching the subject.

According to Cohen (1988), the following is used to interpret the eta square (η^2) value:

.01 - .05	Small
.06 - .13	Medium
.14 and above	Large

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Module’s Suitability, Content, Layout, and Effectiveness According to Experts Module’s Suitability of the Learning Objectives

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of Experts’ Rating on the Module’s Suitability of the Learning Objectives

Particulars	Mean	SD	Rank	Remarks
1. The aims clearly relate to the purpose of the module	4.67	0.52	2.5	SA
2. All the general objectives clearly relate to the purpose of the module	4.83	0.41	1	SA

3. Each set of specific objectives leads to the achievement of its relevant general objectives	4.50	0.55	4	SA
4. All the contents are directly relevant to the objectives	4.67	0.52	2.5	SA
Average	4.67	0.38		SA

It is shown in Table 2 that the learning objectives of the learning module in Automotive Technology are well-suited and constructively aligned (Mean = 4.67, SD = 0.38). In particular, the major aim is well articulated and aligned to the purpose of the module (Mean = 4.83, SD = 0.41), the contents are parallel and responsive to the objectives (Mean = 4.67, SD = .52), and the specific objectives are pertinent to the general objectives (Mean = 4.50, SD = 0.55).

Hence, the experts found the learning module very appropriate in the curriculum of Automotive Technology.

Module's Clarity of Instruction and Test Items

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics of Experts' Rating on the Module's Clarity of Instruction and Test Items

Particulars	Mean	SD	Rank	Remarks
1. All practice task questions have been answered clearly and unambiguously	4.67	0.52	3	SA
2. All instructions are clear and easy to follow	4.50	0.55	4	SA
3. The form and wording of each item in the post-test appropriate for the objective it is intended to assess	4.83	0.41	1.5	SA
4. All post-test questions have been answered clearly and unambiguously	4.83	0.41	1.5	SA
Average	4.71	0.37		SA

Table 3 exposes concerns regarding the measurement and evaluation of the learning modules. As a result, it is manifested from the table that experts concurred that the modules rigorously follow the provisions of clear, proper, and effective test construction (Mean = 4.71, SD = 0.37).

Specifically, the test questions were aptly developed in accordance with the objectives set and were unequivocally stated (Mean = 4.83, SD = 0.41); the practice task questions were very clear (Mean = 4.67, SD = 0.52); and the instructions were explicitly and informatively stated (Mean = 4.50, SD = 0.55).

It can be inferred then that the instructions and test items are thoroughly organized and well-focused.

Module's Suitability of Content

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of Experts' Rating on the Module's Suitability of Content

Particulars	Mean	SD	Rank	Remarks
1. Each unit of the module is in the clear category of the content of the module as a whole	4.50	0.55	8	SA
2. All activities are appropriate for their content and objectives	4.67	0.52	4	SA
3. All learning activities promote active participation and response	4.67	0.52	4	SA
4. Appropriate practice task (feedback) questions and answers have been included at all necessary points	4.50	0.55	8	SA
5. All practice task questions have been interpreted in a satisfactory manner	4.83	0.41	1	SA
6. Practice tasks have been included at all necessary points in a learning sequence	4.67	0.52	4	SA
7. Effective reinforcement statements have been included at necessary points	4.67	0.52	4	SA
8. The module concludes with a comprehensive summary of all main points	4.50	0.55	8	SA
9. The post-test includes at least one item for each specific objective	4.67	0.52	4	SA
Average	4.61	0.34		SA

The directly preceding table projects a consistent decision among experts regarding the module's suitability of content. Generally, experts strongly believed that the modules are very fit in the curriculum (Mean = 4.61, SD = 0.34). In particular, experts were in consensus as their top list is the explicitness and simplicity of practice task questions (Mean = 4.83, SD = 0.41).

Five indicators (Indicators 2, 3, 5, 7, and 9) evenly share the second spot (Mean = 4.67, SD = 0.52). These indicators speak of the modules' learning activities' alignment to set objectives, which encourage maximum participation. Moreover, practice task questions and reinforcements were designed to fix learning points.

One can deduce therefore that the content of the modules is well-planned, designed, and executed to aid the teaching and learning process.

Module's Sequence and Layout

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics of Experts' Rating on the Module's Sequence and Layout

Particulars	Mean	SD	Rank	Remarks
1. The content has been arranged in a logical sequence of learning	4.50	0.55	5.5	SA
2. The unit forms a series of logical steps in the learning sequence	4.67	0.52	2.5	SA
3. All visual elements have been successfully integrated into the learning sequence	4.67	0.52	2.5	SA
4. The layout of the pages is well organized making the module appear interesting and easy to study	4.67	0.52	2.5	SA
5. Whenever appropriate, a touch of humor is added by using cartoons, humorous comments, etc.	4.67	0.52	2.5	SA
6. Satisfactory consolidation passages have been included whenever appropriate	4.50	0.55	5.5	SA

Average	4.61	0.34		SA
---------	------	------	--	----

The content of the modules is logically and sequentially arranged and the provisions for proper layout like the use of visual add-ons were strictly applied, Mean = 4.61, SD = 0.34. The experts strongly perceived the inclusion of passages and humor made the modules more exciting and motivating to read.

In summary, the sequence and layout of the modules unquestionably follow what a good and effective module is.

Rating on the Module's Timing and Phasing

Table 6. Descriptive Statistics of Experts' Rating on the Module's Timing and Phasing

Particulars	Mean	SD	Rank	Remarks
1. Each learning activity is divided into small steps	4.83	0.41	2	SA
2. All learning activities have been planned as input-process-output cycles (I-P-O)	4.67	0.52	4	SA
3. Continuity of learning has been ensured by the inclusion of bridge passage at all necessary points	4.83	0.41	2	SA
4. The length of time needed to complete the module would appear optimal for the type of intended learners	4.83	0.41	2	SA
Average	4.79	0.40		

Table 6 unveils that the module consisting of three lessons is very responsive with respect to timing and phasing dimensions. This is suggested by the computed average rating of experts, which is 4.79, and a scatter index of 0.40 using standard deviation. In detail, the material developer efficiently did a good job in task analysis and coherently embedded the I-P-O theme. Moreover, the continuity of learning is ensured by incorporating passages in the modules.

Hence, the module is considered a learner-centered and -driven material.

Module's Suitability of Approach

Table 7. Descriptive Statistics of Experts' Rating on the Module's Suitability of Approach

Particulars	Mean	SD	Rank	Remarks
1. The module meets a clearly defined need	4.83	0.41	1	SA
2. The purpose of the module has been made clear to all likely users	4.67	0.52	3	SA
3. The module introduction gives a clear account of the scope	4.67	0.52	3	SA
4. The entry behavior of potential users has been carefully described in terms of a comprehensive list of knowledge and skills	4.67	0.52	3	SA
Average	4.71	0.37		SA

Similarly, as compared to previous tables, experts strongly favor the modules' approach as signified by the mean of 4.71, SD = 0.37. In detail, they found out that the development of the modules was out of a dire need in the curriculum (Mean = 4.83, SD

= 0.41); and that this need was reflected and well communicated to users through its extensive and comprehensive scope (Mean = 4.67, SD = 0.52).

As a whole, the approaches blended in the module are efficient and well-defined.

Statistics Summary of Experts' Rating

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics Summary of Experts' Rating

Particulars	Mean	SD	Rank	Remarks
1. Suitability of Aims and Objectives	4.67	0.38	5	SA
2. Clarity of Instructions and Test Items	4.71	0.37	4	SA
3. Suitability of Content	4.63	0.31	6	SA
4. Sequence and Layout	4.61	0.34	7	SA
5. Timing and Phasing	4.79	0.40	1	SA
6. Suitability of Approach	4.72	0.37	3	SA
7. Over-all Effectiveness	4.75	0.39	2	SA
General Average	4.70	0.35		SA

Table 8 provides summary statistics of the experts' ratings regarding the developed learning modules in automotive technology.

As shown, the module has gotten the nod of the experts by acquiring a general average of 4.70, and an SD of 0.35. It was able to pass quality assurance measures. Timing and phasing (Rank 1), effectiveness (Rank 2), and suitability (Rank 3) of the module appear to be the criteria prioritized by the developer. This means that the developer considers the learner as the brain and the heart of the teaching and learning process.

The researcher did not only focus on the substance of the learning material but also was able to meet standards of its form through its sequence and layout (Rank 7).

These only point out that the module can be used by technology education teachers as a response to growing and evolving students' needs and learning styles.

Pre-test Performance

Table 9. Descriptive Statistics of the Pre-test Performances of Students

Group		Min	Max	Mean	SD
Control Group	Module 1	7.00	10.00	9.10	1.10
	Module 2	7.00	10.00	8.40	0.97
	Module 3	7.00	10.00	8.70	1.16
	Average	7.67	9.67	8.73	0.68
Experimental Group	Module 1	7.00	11.00	9.10	1.20
	Module 2	7.00	10.00	8.50	1.08
	Module 3	7.00	10.00	8.20	1.03

	Average	8.00	9.67	8.60	0.62
--	---------	------	------	------	------

The table displays the descriptive statistics of the pre-test performance of students. As gleaned from the table, students' performance from both groups was even in Module 1 (Mean = 9.10) but the control group was less scattered (SD = 1.10, Max = 10) than the experimental group (SD = 1.20, Max = 11). In Module 2, out of the 20-item test, the performance of the students under the control group garnered a lower collective score of 8.40 than the experimental group (Mean = 8.50), and at the same time more homogenous, an SD of 0.97 versus 1.08. Meanwhile, the control group edged out the treatment group in terms of their pre-test performance, 8.70 against 8.20. On average, those who did not utilize the modules had a slim and negligible plus over those who did use the module as shown by the average score of 8.73 against 8.60.

Hence, the entry knowledge rate on average for both groups is 43% to 44% (8.60 or 8.73 divided by 20, the total score). The minimum and maximum scores along all the modules were relatively alike as well.

From the results, the two groups performed at the same level in the pre-test.

Post-test Performance

Table 10. Descriptive Statistics of the Post-test Performances of Students

Group		Min	Max	Mean	SD
Control	Lesson 1	12.00	15.00	13.20	1.23
	Lesson 2	10.00	15.00	12.80	1.55
	Lesson 3	12.00	15.00	13.80	1.03
	Average	12.67	14.33	13.27	0.54
Experimental	Module 1	15.00	18.00	16.00	1.15
	Module 2	15.00	18.00	17.00	1.25
	Module 3	16.00	19.00	17.90	0.99
	Average	16.33	18.33	16.97	0.60

It is evident in the table that after the conduct of the study, students who utilized the three modules were superior and more consistent than those who underwent the traditional chalk-and-talk style as shown by larger means and lower standard deviations. In particular, students who used modular instruction, on average, reaped 16.97 over 20 or a mastery rate of 84.85% compared to 66.35% (13.27 over 20) mastery rate of students who experienced the traditional scheme of instruction. It is also glaring from the table that the maximum scores of students in the control group were the minimum scores of the experimental group.

Hence, the findings lead one to initially conclude that the use of modules, aided students for better reception and retention of concepts and skills in Automotive Technology.

Mean Difference of Pre-Test Performances

Table 11. Independent *T*-test Analysis of Pre-test Performances of Students

		Levene's Test		t-test for Equality of Means					Remarks	Effect Size	
		<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>T</i>	df	<i>p</i>	MD	SE of D		Eta-squared	Remarks
Lesson 1	Equal variances assumed	0.01	.95	0.00	18	1.00	0.00	0.51	NS	.00	Small
Lesson 2	Equal variances assumed	0.22	.67	-0.22	18	.83	-0.10	0.46	NS	.00	Small
Lesson 3	Equal variances assumed	0.24	.63	1.02	18	.32	0.50	0.49	NS	.05	Small
Average	Equal variances assumed	0.00	1.00	0.46	18	.65	0.13	0.29	NS	.01	Small

NS: Not Significant ($p > .05$)

An independent t-test was conducted to test whether there was a significant difference between the pre-test scores of the control and experimental groups. A preliminary check was applied using Levene's Test and it was found out that the variances for the two groups are homogenous along all the three modules, $p > .05$. The t-test when variances are assumed equal yielded no significant difference for Module 1 (MD = 0.00, $t(18) = 0.00$, $p = 1.00$, eta-squared = 0.00, small), Module 2 (MD = -0.10, $t(18) = -0.22$, $p = .83$, eta-squared = 0.00, small), and Module 3 (MD = 0.50, $t(18) = 1.02$, $p = .32$, eta-squared = 0.05, small). Furthermore, the average pre-test in all the modules incurred no significant difference as well (MD = 0.13, $t(18) = 0.46$, $p = 0.65$, eta-squared = 0.01, small).

This implies that the students in the control group, those who did not utilize the module, and the students in the experimental group, who used the module, did not differ in terms of their performance before the actual conduct of the study. It offers an amount of confidence that the two groups have similar entry knowledge and that the result of the post-test is a function of the use or non-use of the module.

Mean Difference of Post-Test Performances

Table 12. Independent *t*-test Analysis of Post-test Performances of Students

		Levene's Test		<i>t</i> -test for Equality of Means					Remarks	Effect Size	
		<i>F</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>t</i>	df	<i>p</i>	MD	SE of D		Eta-squared	Remarks
Lesson 1	Equal variances assumed	0.03	.86	-5.25	18	.00	-2.80	0.53	HS	.60	Large
Lesson 2	Equal variances assumed	0.51	.49	-6.68	18	.00	-4.20	0.63	HS	.71	Large
Lesson 3	Equal variances assumed	0.15	.70	-9.04	18	.00	-4.10	0.45	HS	.82	Large
Average	Equal variances assumed	0.02	.89	-14.53	18	.00	-3.70	0.25	HS	.92	Large

HS: Highly Significant ($p < .01$)

The independent *t*-test was used to determine if a significant difference existed in the post-test results of the students from the two groups. The Levene's test assumes that the variances of the groups along the three modules were similar, $p > .05$. The *t*-test results showed that there is a significant difference between the performance of students who received the treatment and those who did not receive it, $p < .05$. In fact, the difference is highly significant for all the modules, $p < .01$. Furthermore, the results all favor the experimental group over the control group with an average deficit of 3.70.

The difference is large as implied by the computed effect size using eta-squared, .60 - .82, all of which are greater than the threshold value of .14.

These findings stipulate that those who utilized the modules were far better than their counterparts after the conduct of the undertaking. As a result, it is safe to say that their exit knowledge was highly and significantly different because of the use of the modules.

Hence, the use of a module was more effective than the utilization of the traditional chalk-and-chalkboard method.

Conversely, in the work of Johnston (2008) on the educational effectiveness of modular instruction in technology education, he found that students receiving conventional instruction achieved significantly higher test scores than students who experienced modular instruction.

Gains of Learning

Table 13. Descriptive Statistics of the Gains of Learning of Students' Performances

Group		Mean	Mean Gain	SD	SEM	
Control Group	Lesson 1	Pre-test	9.10	4.10	1.10	0.35
		Post-test	13.20		1.23	0.39
	Lesson 2	Pre-test	8.40	4.40	0.97	0.31
		Post-test	12.80		1.55	0.49
	Lesson 3	Pre-test	8.70	5.10	1.16	0.37
		Post-test	13.80		1.03	0.33
	Average	Pre-test	8.73	4.53	0.68	0.22
		Post-test	13.27		0.54	0.17
Experimental Group	Module 1	Pre-test	9.10	6.90	1.20	0.38
		Post-test	16.00		1.15	0.37
	Module 2	Pre-test	8.50	8.50	1.08	0.34
		Post-test	17.00		1.25	0.39
	Module 3	Pre-test	8.20	9.70	1.03	0.33
		Post-test	17.90		0.99	0.31
	Average	Pre-test	8.60	8.37	0.62	0.20
		Post-test	16.97		0.60	0.19

The table exhibits the increase in performance of students in the two groups along the three modules. On average, students' gain in the experimental group is almost twice the improvement of students in the control group (8.37 against 4.53). Moreover, it is also apparent that the mean gain of students for all three modules is up against the students who use the traditional style of teaching. Scrutinizing each of the modules, the highest gain in the control and experimental group was registered in Module 3 (Lubricating System), 5.10 and 9.70, respectively. Module 1, which covers the Cooling System, got the lowest increase for both groups, 4.10 in the control and 6.90 in the experimental group.

The standard deviation and standard error of the mean for all groups along all the modules do not project large deviations, which only means that students' performances were relatively homogenous.

Mean Gain Differences

Table 14. Dependent t-test Analysis of Pre-Test and Post-test Performances of Students

Group	Module No.	<i>T</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	Remarks	Eta-squared	Remarks
Control	Lesson 1	11.78	9	.00	HS	0.94	Large
	Lesson 2	11.85	9	.00	HS	0.94	Large
	Lesson 3	16.22	9	.00	HS	0.97	Large
	Average	19.81	9	.00	HS	0.98	Large
Experimental	Module 1	29.57	9	.00	HS	0.99	Large
	Module 2	21.18	9	.00	HS	0.98	Large
	Module 3	32.33	9	.00	HS	0.99	Large
	Average	57.92	9	.00	HS	1.00	Large

HS: Highly Significant ($p < .01$)

To check whether there is a significant increase in students' performance from the pre-test to the post-test after the use and non-use of learning modules in automotive technology, the dependent t-test was used.

In general, both groups in all modules exhibited a significant increase, $p < .05$. In the control, students progressed ominously in all three lessons ($p < .05$) with Lesson 3 having the highest improvement as indicated by the largest *t*-index value followed by the Lesson 2, then Lesson 1.

In the experimental group, those who received modular instruction, students were able to demonstrate growth as specified by the *p-values* of less than .05, which is .00. Similarly in the control group, it is sufficient to say that the improvement of the students was highly significant. The significant improvements are all supported by the eta-squared values of .9 and above.

In a capsule, students who used the modular instruction were able to learn successfully. Comparing the learning gain, however, it is noted that a grander advancement was recorded in the modular instruction. This in effect offers two directions: first, the use of traditional and modular instruction are both effective approaches to technology education and second, the use of modular instruction is one of the good alternatives in teaching technology education but can never be a replacement for traditional instruction.

Hence, the use of modular instruction should be motivated with a noble purpose, stirred by the needs of the students and one that encourages independent and lifelong learning among the prospective students.

Based on the results of the research study, there is no significant difference in the pre-test scores of the students exposed to the traditional and modular approaches. Thus, the hypothesis number one (1) is accepted.

The result of the research study also revealed that there is a significant difference in the post-test scores of the students exposed to the traditional and modular approaches. Thus, the hypothesis number two (2) is rejected.

Finally, this research study found that there is a significant difference in the learning gain scores of the students exposed to the traditional and modular approaches. This means that the hypothesis number three (3) is also rejected.

Conclusions

In view of the findings, this study concludes that the developed learning modules in Automotive Technology are highly effective in supporting students' learning. Experts evaluated the modules positively, highlighting their alignment with curriculum objectives, clarity of instruction, and suitability of content. The modules were well-structured with logically sequenced content, which was enhanced by the effective integration of visual aids, humor, and reinforcement statements, making them both engaging and conducive to learning. The study's results further indicated that students who utilized the modules outperformed those who underwent traditional instruction in the post-test, demonstrating greater comprehension and retention. This affirms the modules' capacity to facilitate mastery of skills in Automotive Technology, suggesting their potential as a valuable instructional tool. Hence, the modules can significantly contribute to enhancing educational practices in automotive technology courses, addressing diverse learning needs, and promoting learner-centered education.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Automotive Teachers are encouraged to adopt the validated learning modules in their instruction to provide structured, interactive, and learner-centered materials that align with curriculum goals. By using these modules, they can better support students' mastery of complex topics in automotive technology.
2. School administrators should consider adopting validated learning modules as a standard resource in technical and vocational courses. Investing in these resources can significantly enhance instructional quality and consistency, which benefits both teachers and students in developing essential skills.
3. Students are encouraged to actively engage with modular learning materials, as these resources are designed to reinforce understanding and retention. Modules offer self-paced learning opportunities that can improve concept mastery and build confidence in technical subjects.
4. Researchers are encouraged to conduct further validation studies on learning modules across different subjects and levels. Expanding research on instructional materials can

enhance the quality of resources available and inform best practices in module design and implementation.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author adheres to ethical standards. Informed consent was obtained, and respondents could withdraw at any time. Anonymity was maintained, and their well-being was safeguarded. There were no conflicts of interest, and plagiarism was strictly avoided. I ensured an unbiased interpretation of the findings, and the results were intended solely for research purposes.

Acknowledgments

The author is deeply grateful to his research adviser for the expert guidance and encouragement. Sincere thanks to the respondents for their participation, and to his colleagues for their support. His heartfelt appreciation goes to his family, friends, and relatives for their constant encouragement. Above all, he thanks God for the strength and wisdom to complete this research.

REFERENCES

- Adu, E.O. (2021). Managing Social Studies Education Curriculum for National Development.
- Apostol, E.M., Apolonio, A.M., Jose, B.R., Garingan, E.G., & Bautista, R.G. (2016). Optimizing Classroom Instruction through Online Instructional Delivery Technique. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 4, 302-306.
- Chen, Z., & Wang, Q. (2014). Examining Classroom Interactional Practices to Promote Learning in the Young Learner EFL Classroom in China.
- Chuks, O.J., & Nebechi, N.F. (2016). Comparative Study of the Impact of Instructional Materials and Technology on Traditional and Distance Education Systems. *International journal for innovation education and research*, 4, 71-78.
- Ghani, M.R., & Abdullah, A.B. (2002). Technical and Vocational Education in Malaysia.
- Jahantab, Z. (2021). Role of Education in National Development.
- Johnston, R. J. (2008). A comparative analysis between the effectiveness of conventional and modular instruction in teaching students with varied learning styles and individual differences, enrolled in high school industrial arts manufacturing. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 47(8), 2923A.
- Kistner, S., Rakoczy, K., Otto, B., Klieme, E., & Büttner, G. (2015). Teaching learning strategies. The role of instructional context and teacher beliefs. *Journal for educational research online*, 7, 176-197.
- Maiwada, U.D. (2022). Introductory Technology as It Impacts Modern Society in The World. *Journal of Technology Innovations and Energy*.
- Manabat, T. (2021). Modular Print Materials: Philippine Way of Learning Delivery In Times Of New Normal. *AJARCDE | Asian Journal of Applied Research for Community Development and Empowerment* .

- Mangundayao, A.B., Briones, S.J., & Mefragata, J.D. (2001). SUSTAINING TECHNICIAN EDUCATION IN THE AGE OF GLOBALIZATION.
- Miller, M., & Veatch, N.C. (2010). Teaching Literacy in Context: Choosing and Using Instructional Strategies. *The Reading Teacher*, 64, 154-165.
- Odo, J., Okafor, W.C., Odo, A.L., Ejikeugwu, L.N., & Ugwuoke, C. (2017). Technical Education - The Key to Sustainable Technological Development. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 5, 1878-1884.
- Parsons, S.A., & Vaughn, M. (2014). A Multiple Case Study of Two Teachers' Instructional Adaptations. *Alberta Journal of Educational Research*.
- Ramos, A.C. (2015). Methods and Teaching Strategies Used by Teacher Education Faculty Members in one State University in the Philippines. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3, 36-44.
- Ricard, V.B. (1990). Techniques: Developing Learning Modules for Adults. *Journal of Adult Education*, 18.
- Ricardo, J. L. (2016). Development and validation of learning modules in physics (Unpublished master's thesis). Cagayan State University, Tuguegarao City, Philippines.
- Victory, D. (2011). EDUCATION AND SOCIETAL DEVELOPMENT: THE QUALITY IMPERATIVE.
-